

Teachers' Perceived English Proficiency and Self-Efficacy of English Teachers in the Academic World

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ABSTRACT: This research used descriptive correlational design to find the significant relationship between perceived English proficiency and self-efficacy of English teachers.

The respondents of the study were 142 elementary teachers teaching English in Candelaria West District. It was conducted during the third quarter of SY 2022-2023. Majority of the respondents are within 26-30 and 41-45 years of age, mostly are female, majority of them are in the service for less than five years, with Bachelor Degree, graduate of Education but non-English major, and majority of them use English every day outside the classroom. The respondents use English in a week mainly in teaching an English class. The respondents perceived reading as their most proficient macro skills and speaking, their least proficient.

They perceived general English proficiency, speaking skill, and writing skill in the proficient level while listening and reading skills in the highly proficient level. The respondents perceived efficacy to decision making, efficacy to influence resources, instructional efficacy, and efficacy to parental involvement, community and stakeholders in some influence level. Meanwhile, disciplinary self-efficacy and efficacy to create a positive school climate in a great deal level.

When it is correlated the results revealed that majority of the self-perceptions in English proficiency are correlated to self-efficacy. However, certain variables found to have no significant relationship to each other. This includes the general English proficiency and the four macro skills to efficacy to influence decision making, efficacy to influence resources and efficacy to parental involvement, community and stakeholders both for writing skills.

KEYWORDS: General English Proficiency, Perceived English Proficiency, Self- Efficacy

INTRODUCTION

Competency issues are always at the forefront for English teachers. As English language teachers, a certain proficiency level in the language to teach is of great importance as to provide the students with valuable input that can help them learn. Likewise, effective classroom delivery of the subject content (Elder, 200, Wang, C., 2021).

Thus, when an English teacher has a low English competence, it can contribute to poor student's English communication performance (Gultom 2013). Research shows that perceive importance of English proficiency and communication skills are predictors of academic performance. As students continue their university education, they must possess ample learning experiences and effective communication competence level for successful learning.

In the Philippines, scholarly teaching and learning of English in every school is very apparent. It can be seen from the day-to-day instruction and activities given to students in an English classroom. It is believed that a good and competent English teacher in a classroom matter. Our country, considered as one of the countries with some degree of fluency in terms of communication, problems in English communication still arise. Based on a recent roundtable discussion organized by the British Council, Philippines, despite being one of the largest English-speaking nations, the country needs to step up its effort and improving the teaching and learning of English, to strengthen the Philippines distinct advantage of English communication in this part of the world. And this lies on the teacher's competence to teach and develop the communication skills of the students who will join in the workforce in the near future (Cabigon, 2015).

Thus, upskilling teachers in English is important since some research studies found teacher's English proficiency correlates with their ability to provide optimal learning opportunities in an English classroom.

In today's global world, English is the most widely spoken language in the world, so its importance cannot be denied or ignored. With the development of technology, English plays an important role in many fields such as medicine, engineering and education, and is considered the most important field where English is needed. Studies shows that Philippines, being a second language speakers of English, the proficiency level of the students in English has deteriorated over time. To address this, the government

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issued Executive Order 210 CHED Memo No.20 s.2013 where English is the medium of instruction in English, Math and Sciences to continuously improve English acquisition of students. Thus, the big piece of responsibility to address the gap, is to have qualified and competent English teachers with high proficiency level to ensure quality learning in the classroom.

A number of studies have been conducted in recent decades to examine the relationship between teachers' language skills and self-efficacy. This is a concept related to teachers' belief in their ability to effectively manage work-related tasks, responsibilities, and assignments. It is said that, it plays an important role in influencing important academic outcomes (e.g. student's achievement and motivation) and well-being in the working environment. Moreover, teacher's self-efficacy progressively gained an important role in school psychology research as a result of its implications for teaching effectiveness, instructional practices, and for students' academic achievement (Klassen et al., 2009; Klassen and Tze, 2014, Barni, et.al. 2019).

There is also considerable research that teachers with high levels of self-efficacy experience higher levels of job satisfaction, lower levels of job-related stress and face less difficulties in dealing with students' misbehaviors. Thus, examining teacher's Self-English Proficiency level and understanding the antecedent of teacher's self-efficacy may provide us better results to design a strategic training of language of instruction skills to English teachers who are not so proficient in English since studies show that language instruction and language of interaction have a high correlation with teaching self-efficacy.

The concept of English as a language of instruction means that the teacher's language is used to teach academic subjects such as English, mathematics and science. This functional nature of the language used in an English classroom maybe reflected by the two constructs; language of instruction and language of interaction according to CLA (Education Bureau of Hongkong 2011). Language of instruction refers to the fluency in the in the language use in teaching the students while language of interaction is a conversation or small talk in the class where teachers can use formal or casual expressions properly depending on the situation. It also refers to selecting vocabulary appropriate to the topic (Clifford, 2022). In this study, the self-perception of English proficiency Test by Kaewwichian and Jaturapitakkul (2018) of University of Technology Thonburi, an adapted test from the CEFR framework and focusing on descriptive item will be used. This comprises statements on general English Proficiency, Listening Skill, Reading Skill, and Writing Skill.

Another theory that was used in this study is Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory (1977, 1986, 1997). Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in their ability to perform the actions necessary to achieve a particular performance outcome. It also reflects confidence in one's motivations, behavior, and ability to control one's social environment. The researcher will use Bandura's Instrument to measure Teacher's Self- Efficacy Scale with seven sub factors to measure. The theoretical framework below defines the variables that were used in this study.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to find out the relationship between the teachers' Self-Perceptions towards English Proficiency and their Self-Efficacy. Specifically, it sought to find out the profile of the respondents in terms of: age, sex, years of teaching experience, educational attainment, area of specialization, and number of times in using English language outside the classroom. It also aimed to find out the type of activities involving the use of English the teacher-respondents typically exposed to or involved in during a week. Additionally, in which English Macro Skills are the respondents most and least proficient to?

It also aimed to find out the perceived level of English Proficiency of the teacher respondents in terms of: General English Proficiency, Listening Skill, Reading Skill, Speaking Skill, and Writing Skill. Also, the perceived level of self-efficacy of the teacher- respondents in terms of: Influence in Decision Making, Influence School Resources, Instructional Efficacy, Disciplinary Self-Efficacy, Parental and Community Stakeholders, and Create a Positive School Climate.

This study aimed to find out if there is a significant relationship between the respondents' self-perceptions towards English proficiency and their self-efficacy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

In this study, the descriptive correlational method was used to describe the relationship between teachers' perceived English proficiency and self-efficacy of English teachers.

RESPONDENTS OF THE STUDY

The respondents of the study were the English teachers of public elementary schools of Candelaria West District in Quezon. The eleven (11) schools included in the study are hereby presented.

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Table 1

Distribution of Teacher Respondents

School	Sample
A	5
B	5
C	7
D	7
E	13
F	23
G	23
H	18
I	8
J	10
K	6
TOTAL	142

Total enumeration of the respondents was utilized to get higher number of responses for higher reliability and internal validity of the results. This was conducted in the school year 2022-2023 of the third quarter. Adapted and modified survey questionnaire from Self-perception of English Proficiency of Thai Lower Secondary EFL Teachers, Bangkok, Thailand and Bandura's Instrument Teacher Self- Efficacy Scale were used in the study.

Research Instrument

To get the self-perceptions English Proficiency of the English teacher-respondents adapted under the framework of the Common European Framework of References (CEFR). This instrument was also used by Kaewwichian and Jaturapitakkul of King Monkut's University of Technology, Thailand who examined the self-perceptions of English proficiency with same instrument. The research instrument of this study is a four-point Likert scale questionnaire which included two parts: demographic information and self-perception towards English proficiency. The first part elicited participants' personal information in terms of their general and educational background, teaching experience and their use of English.

The second part consisted of 37 items with a scale of 1 – 4, ranging from strongly disagree (=1) to strongly agree (= 4). All items used elicited how the participants perceive their English proficiency. The questionnaire was constructed by adapting the CEFR framework and focusing on descriptive items. All 37 selected items are broken down into five sub-sections: 1) General English proficiency (10 items); 2) Listening skill (5 items); 3) Reading skill (6 items); 4) Speaking skill (10 items); and 5) Writing skill (6 items).

The third part of the instrument consists of statements to get the self-efficacy of the English teacher-respondents. Bandura's self-efficacy scale instrument is adapted containing questionnaire that are designed to help teachers gain better understanding of the kind of things that create difficulties in the teacher's school activities. This questionnaire consists of 1-4 scales from nothing to a great deal descriptive scale.

The two instruments are entirely written in English and easy to understand. The researcher hopes that the use of this instrument will be answered by the respondents with all honesty and responses will be treated with confidentiality.

Since the instrument was modified in the context of Filipino English teachers, the instrument still undergone Cronbach analysis for internal validity and reliability. Pilot testing was done to get the views of the respondents who are not included in the study.

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Table 2
Perceived Teacher's English Proficiency and Self-Efficacy

Subscale	No. of Items	Cronbach Alpha Result	Interpretation
English Proficiency			
General English Proficiency	10	.951	Excellent
Listening	5	.799	Acceptable
Reading	6	.875	Good
Speaking	10	.946	Excellent
Writing	6	.968	Excellent
Self-Efficacy			
Efficacy to Influence Decision Making	2	.792	Acceptable
Efficacy to Influence Resources	2	1.0	Excellent
Instructional Efficacy	8	.959	Excellent
Disciplinary Self-Efficacy	3	.772	Acceptable
Efficacy to Parental Involvement, Community and Stakeholders	6	.901	Excellent
Efficacy to Create a Positive School Climate	7	.833	Good

Legend: $a \geq 0.9$ Excellent, $0.9 > a \geq 0.8$ Good, $0.8 > a \geq 0.7$ Acceptable, $0.7 > a \geq 0.6$ Questionable, $0.6 > a \geq 0.5$ Poor, $0.5 > a$ Unacceptable

Presented on the table is the result of Cronbach analysis of the instrument for external validity and reliability. Cronbach's alpha is a way of assessing reliability by comparing the amount of shared variance, or covariance, among the items making up an instrument to the amount of overall variance. The idea is that if the instrument is reliable, there should be a great deal of covariance among the items relative to the variance (L.M. Collins, 2007). It also means that Cronbach's alpha is a convenient test used to estimate the reliability, or internal consistency, of a composite score (statisticssolutions.com,2022). Since the figures presented are more than .70, the instruments on perceived English proficiency and self-efficacy passed the reliability and validity test viable for the conduct of the study. It can be seen from the scores presented have the higher percentage than that of 70%. Both self-perceived English proficiency and self-efficacy passed with excellent rating.

RESEARCH PROCEDURE

In the conduct of the study, the researcher prepared first the instrument to be used in the survey. Careful reading and analysis of the different types of questionnaire was done to get the best instrument that will capture the purpose of this study. After reading several researches and studies, the instrument and manuscript was submitted to the panel members and adviser for final approval and for research proposal.

After the proposal, suggestions were considered and revisions were made. The researcher then had the questionnaires validated by three external validators; one (1) School Head, one (1) Master Teacher, and one (1) Field expert. After the comments and suggestions of the validators were incorporated in the survey questionnaires these were submitted to subject specialist for further checking.

Upon approval of the subject specialist, the researcher had an online consultation with the statistician and was given the signal to begin the pilot testing with 10 teachers which are not part of the actual respondents. Hard copies of questionnaires were given during the pilot testing.

After the pilot testing, the results were tabulated in the data matrix template and was submitted to the statistician for Cronbach Alpha analysis.

The questionnaires passed the Cronbach Alpha, then the data gathering process for the study started.

The researcher personally went to the eleven (11) schools of Candelaria West District starting with the small schools then to large ones. The researcher presented the letter of permission to conduct the study to the principals, head teachers, and teachers-in-charge of every school. After the discussion about the purpose of the study and the content of the questionnaires, the hard copies were distributed to the respondents of the study.

The questionnaires were retrieved from schools after one week from distribution. To ensure 100% retrieval, the researcher herself, collected the questionnaires and made sure of its completeness in number by coordinating with the teacher in charge of distribution and retrieval of survey questionnaires.

For ethical consideration, the researcher sought the permission from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Quezon Province and the Office of the District Supervisor of Candelaria West District for the conduct of the study. The assistance of the school principals was requested for a smooth and successful retrieval of the instrument. The data were gathered, tabulated and submitted to the statistician for the checking.

After all the prescribed requirements were accomplished and submitted, the data was submitted to the university's Stat Center for statistical treatment.

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Statistical treatment

For better analysis and discussions, the following statistical tools were used.

To get the self-perceptions proficiency and self-efficacy, mean and standard deviation was used with a 1-4-point scale. To find out the significant relationship of the dependent and independent variables, Pearson Moment Correlation was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3

Summary of Results for Self-perceptions towards English Proficiency

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
General English Proficiency	3.4	0.42	Proficient
Listening Skill	3.5	0.47	Highly Proficient
Reading Skill	3.6	0.47	Highly Proficient
Speaking Skill	3.3	0.44	Proficient
Writing Skill	3.4	0.49	Proficient
Overall	3.4	0.46	Proficient

Table 10 shows the summary of results for Self-perceptions towards English Proficiency of the English teachers of Candelaria West District. Based from the table, the respondents are highly proficient in both listening and reading skills.

When listening, respondents are able to identify familiar words and basic phrases about themselves, their families, and their immediate and specific environment when spoken slowly and clearly. This suggests that they are confidently engaging in meaningful activities, including listening, especially if it helps them improve their skills to achieve more desirable learning outcomes. Short, clear and simple messages and announcements can also capture the essence. This is necessary for teachers to be effective school officials.

In terms of reading comprehension, all the indicators got highly proficient result, because reading is an integral part of learning. As a teacher, achieving the highest level of reading comprehension is a must. This result suggests that respondents can easily recognize simple phrases on notices and posters. They can read and understand both short and long sentences. They can find specific and predictable information in advertisements, menus, timetables and other materials. They can easily understand personal letters, e-mails and other messages written in English, which helps them not only in class but also in carrying out domestic affairs.

On the other hand, the speaking skill average mean was the lowest at 3.3, meaning, respondents rated themselves as still competent in this skill although their level of confidence in carrying out tasks related to this skill is not as high of that of reading skill. Respondents may enter conversations unprepared on familiar, personal, or everyday topics. And even if they don't use the language often, they can handle social sharing. Additionally, respondents can easily justify and explain their opinions and plans. While these are all positive responses, this suggests that teachers are not entirely confident in their speaking ability. Because they are not native speakers, they cannot confidently speak the language for fear of making grammatical mistakes.

Table 4

Summary of Results for Perceptions of the Respondents on the Teachers' Self-Efficacy

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Efficacy to Influence Decision Making	3.1	0.58	Some influence
Efficacy to Influence Resources	3.3	0.57	Some influence
Instructional Efficacy	3.3	0.43	Some influence
Disciplinary Self-Efficacy	3.5	0.54	A great deal
Efficacy to Parental Involvement, Community and Stakeholders	3.2	0.55	Some influence
Efficacy to Create a Positive School Climate	3.5	0.49	A great deal
Overall	3.32	0.53	Some influence

Legend: 3.50-4.00-A great deal, 2.50-3.49 Some influence, 1.50-2.49- Very little, 1.00- 1.49- Nothing

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The table show the summary of results for perceptions of the respondents on the teachers' self- efficacy.

Based on the results, Disciplinary Self-Efficacy and Efficacy to Create a Positive School Climate got the highest mean of 3.5, which indicates that the respondents have a great deal of self-efficacy in these aspects.

It is almost natural for a teacher to have an excellent disciplinary measure as it is reflected in their effective classroom management. Teachers can effectively get children follow classroom rules, likewise, although most of the time very challenging and stressful, teachers have ways of controlling disruptive behavior in the classroom.

When it comes to efficacy to create positive school climate, the respondents, are confident that they can contribute so much to make the school a safe place for the learners. They believe that their opinions and suggestions are being heard and considered in making school policies and regulations. In addition, teachers have many creative ways of making students enjoy coming to school. They have a wide variety of strategies to keep the students motivated and excited to come to school every day. Teachers are also well-aware that their students trust them. This is evident in their small or even serious conversation during or after class. Being the second parent of the child, teachers are compassionate with their students, which in turn make the child trust them wholeheartedly. The result also shows that teachers believe that they are capable of enhancing collaboration between their co-teachers and administration to make school run effectively. They believe that they can make valuable input which will eventually result in the effective implementation of the schools' policies and guidelines.

However, among the seven (7) indicators, Efficacy to Influence Decision Making got the lowest mean of 3.1. This means that the respondents believe that they only have some influence in decision making about matters not concerning teaching and learning. The respondents believe that they have a fair influence in the decisions made in the school. Also, based from the result, the respondents can somehow express their views freely on important school matters, but not with utmost confidence.

Table 5

Correlation Between Self-Perceptions Towards English Proficiency and their Self-Efficacy

English Proficiency	Efficacy to Influence Decision Making	Efficacy to Influence Resources	Instructional Efficacy	Disciplinary Self Efficacy	Efficacy to Parental Involvement, Community and Stakeholders	Efficacy to Create a Positive School Climate
	r-value	r-value	r-value	r-value	r-value	r-value
General English Proficiency	.133	.289**	.403**	.339**	.168*	.327**
Listening Skill	.116	.203*	.393**	.236**	.199*	.201*
Reading Skill	.098	.105	.379**	.275**	.181*	.153
Speaking Skill	.130	.181*	.377**	.313**	.202*	.201*
Writing Skill?	.074	.164	.353**	.258**	.071	.169*

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The table shows the results of the significant relationship between self-perceptions in English proficiency and their self-efficacy to influence resources, instructional efficacy, disciplinary self-efficacy, efficacy to parental involvement, community and stakeholders, and efficacy to create a positive school climate. Based on the figures above perceived general English proficiency is significantly related to efficacy to influence resources with an R-value of .289, instructional efficacy with .403 R-value, disciplinary self-efficacy with .339 R-value, efficacy to parental involvement with .168 R-value and efficacy to create a positive school climate with a R-value of .327 all at 0.01 level of significance. These results show that the positive perception of the respondents on their General English proficiency has a positive effect on their self-efficacy. This is supported by the study of Wang (2021) who examined the relationship between English proficiency and their self-efficacy and found to have a strong positive relationship. This only show that the English proficiency of teachers helps foster the achievement and maintenance of higher teacher self-efficacy in all aspects. The researcher believes that teachers with high English proficiency level have the better chance of influencing people, have the ability to collaborate effectively across cultures, borders and languages, proficiency is a non-negotiable skill where English language skills are key (pearson.com, 2021).

In terms of listening skill, it is found significantly related to efficacy to influence resources with an R-value of .203, instructional efficacy with an R-value of .393, disciplinary self-efficacy with R-value of .236, efficacy to parental involvement, community and stakeholders with an R-value of .199 and efficacy to create a positive school climate with an R-value of .201 all at .01 level of significance. Results indicate that the positive self-perceptions of teachers' listening skill has a great effect on their self-efficacy. This result is supported by Chaturverdi (2021) who suggested that teachers who have higher English proficiency level have better chance of effective instruction as well as maintaining discipline in the classroom (engage-education.com (2020). Moreover,

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significant relationship to parental involvement and creating positive climate is supported by Delgado believing that teachers with good listening skills when communicating with parents as well as with other stakeholders' benefits students and teachers for the achievement of successful learning and development of student's skills. Likewise, it resulted to creating positive climate that benefits everyone in the school. It also increases achievement and promote mental and physical well-being of teacher and students (CFR, 2019).

Positive self-perceptions of the respondents toward reading skill also found to be significantly related to self-efficacy in terms instructional efficacy with an R-value of .379, disciplinary self-efficacy with .275 R-value, efficacy to parental involvement and community with .181 R-value, and efficacy to create positive climate with an R-value of .153. These results indicate that if the teachers have positive English proficiency it would significantly affect self-efficacy of different terms. This is supported by pearson.com (2022), that when a teacher has the capacity to communicate with people effectively and has the proficiency in the four macro skills of the language, they have the ability to collaborate effectively across cultures, and have the better chance of influencing people. Thus, proficiency is a non-negotiable skill where English language skills are the key.

As to positive self-perceptions of the teachers/respondent's English proficiency in terms of speaking skill, it is found to significantly correlated to self-efficacy. This can be seen for the results of R-values at 0.01 level of significance. These R-values are .181 for efficacy to influence resources, .377 for instructional efficacy, .313 for disciplinary self-efficacy, .202 for efficacy for parental involvement and community and .201 for efficacy to create positive climate. These results imply that the English proficiency of teachers significantly influence their self-efficacy. It only means that when an individual has the speaking skill to communicate any ideas, opinions, information to people, he/she can easily charmed people to listen and speak out their ideas too and meet at the center. In the same manner, when a teacher has the eloquence to express his/her ideas, definitely, school leaders, parents and even the community will listen and understand his/her ideas and opinions as long it will benefit many. Masduki et al. (2022) stated that teachers with high English proficiency leads to felicitous decision of the classroom behavior communication behavior. Thus, significant relationship is expected.

Lastly, self-perceptions in English proficiency in terms of writing skill found to be significantly correlated to self-efficacy of the teachers. This includes instructional efficacy with .353 R-value, disciplinary self-efficacy with .258 R-value, efficacy to parental involvement and community with .071 R-value and efficacy in creating positive climate with .169 R-value all at 0.01 level of significance. These results imply that teacher's English proficiency is of great importance and influence in the teaching profession. Communication with students, parents school heads and community are expected from teachers, thus, skills in speaking and writing are major competencies to be mastered. Mastery of the four macro skills in English or having the proficiency in English is an advantage to teachers since most of the time they communicate with different people. Likewise, it enhances the instructional competencies that leads to desired outcomes of student's engagement and learning in the classroom. Hong Shi (2018), examined the teacher's instructional efficacy found to have significant effect to self-efficacy. In the same manner, teachers with good English proficiency.

From the results obtained, the positive self-perceptions of Candelaria West District teachers' English proficiency significantly influence their self-efficacy. Results highlighted the positive perceptions toward the four macro skills which include reading, listening, speaking and writing. Based on the discussions presented, when a teacher possesses the skills in English, it has great effect in the classroom instruction, classroom management, participate in decision making, discipline among students, motivation to parents and community involvement and creating positive climate in the classroom for better learning is very evident. Thus, English exposure, and continuous use of the English language would enhance more their proficiency since the respondents involved in the study are not English majors but teaching English. Moreover, they frequently use English in the class but not outside the classroom. Seldom they use in daily lives. Overall, positive self-perceptions towards English proficiency have a great deal of relationship to teacher's self-efficacy.

However, the variables that are not correlated are; decision making to general English proficiency, to the four macro skills. This indicates that, proficiency in the four macro skills do not have influence on their efficacy to decision making. The results revealed no correlation which may mean that whether a teacher is proficient in the English language or not, as long it is need to be part of the decision making, he/she can influence the leaders to let him/her participate and express opinions and ideas. Likewise, efficacy to influence to resources found to be not correlated with writing skill as well as efficacy to parental involvement, community and stakeholders. This may also suggest that proficiency of the teachers in writing has nothing to do with self-efficacy in terms of the variables previously discussed. This only indicates that to influence provision of resources, and parental involvement and community, writing skill not necessarily mean no influence at all. It could mean positive results that whether the teacher is proficient or not in writing, he/she can still influence the leaders to provide instructional and learning resources for the student's welfare

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results presented, the following conclusions are drawn. There are positive self-perceptions of the respondents in their General English proficiency (Proficient), Listening Skill (Highly Proficient), Reading Skill (Highly Proficient), Speaking Skill (Proficient), and Writing Skill (Proficient), based on the responses of agreement given to each indicator.

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There is positive self-efficacy of the respondents in terms of influence to Decision Making (Some Influence), Influence Resources (Some influence), Instructional Efficacy (Some Influence), Disciplinary Self Efficacy (Great Deal), Parental Involvement, Community and Stakeholders (Some Influence), and Create a Positive School Climate (Great Deal) based on the responses given. There is significant relationship between self-perceived English proficiency and self-efficacy. However, there are a number of self-perceived English proficiency variables that have no correlation to self-efficacy. These are, general English proficiency and four macro skills and efficacy to decision making. Writing skill has no significant relationship to efficacy to influence resources and efficacy to parental involvement community and stakeholders. Thus, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between self-perceptions towards English proficiency and Self-Efficacy is rejected. However, Efficacy to Influence Decision Making and English Proficiency has no significant relationship.

Established from the summary of findings and conclusions previously discussed and presented, the following recommendations are hereby suggested.

Teachers may attend more conferences, seminars and trainings towards English proficiency to enhance more their abilities in the four macro skills such as listening, reading, writing and speaking since majority of the teachers teaching English are not major of the English language.

Teachers may train themselves to use the English language not only in their class but also in everyday conversation outside the school to improve their speaking and writing skills needed in an English class to serve as role model to their students.

Develop more their English competencies in the four macro skills to have better communication skills through a lot of reading, attending language trainings, exposure to English speaking environment such as movies, media broadcast, conversations and other English language related activities.

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